

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Ice Age Geology of the Great Barrier Reef

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FK201122
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor</i>
Expedition Name	Ice Age Geology of the Great Barrier Reef
Expedition Dates	2020/11/22 - 2020/12/22
Departure Port	Brisbane, Australia
Termination Port	Brisbane, Australia
Ocean	South Pacific Ocean

1.0.0.1 Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Twenty thousand years ago, during the last ice age, most of Earth's water was locked in ice and glaciers. The sea level around Australia's coastline was approximately 100 to 120 meters lower than today, exposing the continental shelf, including areas where coral grows. A narrow band of coral reef thrived in the location of what is now the edge of the continental shelf of east Australia. As sea level rose, the coral reef drowned, and the ocean covered a number of landscapes unique to the Australian continent. The upper continental slope and shelf edge of the southern Great Barrier Reef are largely unknown and poorly mapped. After a successful expedition mapping the [northern Great Barrier Reef](#), R/V *Falkor* traversed to the southern reaches of the Great Barrier Reef World Heritage Area to continue its mapping efforts.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
G20/43838.1 V3	Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority	Scientific research
G19/39364.1	Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority	Scientific research

Table 1: Permits obtained for this expedition's operations and sample collection.

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition commenced on November 22, 2020, departing from Brisbane, Australia, and returned to Brisbane, Australia, on December 22, 2020.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The goal of the expedition was to explore ancient undersea features that formed during the last Ice Age, when sea level was almost 120 m lower than it is today. To reveal the topography of these drowned landscapes, the expedition plan was to systematically survey the Fraser and Capricorn-Bunker shelf, the Capricorn Channel, and the edges and slopes of the southern Swain Reefs. The Capricorn-Bunker and Swain Reefs make up the southern extent of the present-day Great Barrier Reef (GBR) and mark the transition from tropical to temperate ocean conditions to the south.

The science team aimed to determine whether the drowned reef system that had been extensively mapped in the northern and central portion of the GBR resembled the drowned reefs located in the southern GBR, or whether such drowned reefs extended far south at all.

Additionally, the science team aimed to understand better the southern extent of an even older limestone platform, which may represent the ~20 million-year-old base upon which the present Great Barrier Reef has grown. The science team on board R/V *Falkor* used high-resolution multibeam data to search for these past shorelines, drowned reefs,

pinnacles, and shelf-edge terraces, as well as ancient river channels and deltas that connect to the ocean basin (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Overview map of southern Great Barrier Reef, southern Swain Reefs, Capricorn-Bunker Group reefs, and science survey areas mapped during FK201122.

To complement the mapping campaign, the science team measured the water column subsurface current strength, direction, and temperature of the locally important Capricorn Eddy, which is thought to provide important nutrients and cool water to the Capricorn-Bunker and Swain Reefs during spring and summer.

Additionally, the expedition measured atmospheric aerosol particles produced by coral reefs. Corals produce aerosols naturally, which can create cloud cover, protecting the corals from harsh sunlight. An aerosol sampler was used to collect data that will be used by the Reef Restoration and Adaptation Program to investigate technologies to reduce coral bleaching by creating cloud cover. This data will help create more robust atmospheric models to be added to the CSIRO eReefs hydrodynamic models.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

Systematic multibeam data acquisition was concentrated over six areas of interest (Figure 2). Areas 1 to 5 were directly related to the specific objectives of the expedition, and Area 6 was mapped during the return to port, to fill gaps in multibeam seabed mapping of the Fraser Canyon and upper continental slope connecting the southern Great Barrier Reef shelf to the deep ocean.

The expedition completed the most comprehensive systematic multibeam mapping of the southern extent of the GBR along the shelf-edge and upper continental slope. The science team mapped 400 km of submerged shoreline and systematically mapped the 50 to 220-meter depth range (Figure 2). This depth range is significant because it contains geologically and ecologically significant submerged features that formed between 10,000 to 20,000 years ago when sea level was up to 120 meters lower than today. The maps created, revealed the drowned reef terraces, pinnacles, beaches and shorelines, river channels, and deltas that the science team sought to capture. Sea levels progressively transgressed the continental shelf, inundating past shoreline and reef features.

In total (including transits), more than 13,000 km² of multibeam bathymetry was added to the AusSeabed Australian national data collection, captured on this expedition.

Survey Area 1

The voyage transited from the port of Brisbane to the first science survey area via the continental shelf edge east of K'gari (Fraser Island). The voyage track was aligned parallel to previous multibeam tracks to supplement the progressive mapping of the upper continental slope and shelf edge.

A multibeam bathymetry survey was conducted along the -90 to -250 m isobath seaward of Lady Elliot Island to Heron Reef, capturing the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) shelf-edge shoreline (Figure 3). Mapping revealed active bedforms perpendicular to the ship track in depths from -240 to -280 m, with up to 10 m height amplitude from dune crest to swale (Figure 4). These bedforms are indicative of current action associated with active southeast-to-northwest longshore drift parallel to the shelf-edge.

Figure 3: Survey area 1 multibeam coverage and locations of sediment samples collected proximal to the Capricorn Group reefs shelf-edge.

Figure 4: Profile along active bedforms shows dunes with up to 10 m height amplitude (top); and profile across a newly mapped drowned reef system seaward of Heron Reef shows stepped sea level-related terraces and knick points (bottom).

Systematic mapping was also conducted seaward of Heron and One Tree Reefs in approximately -50 to -65 m depth. This mapping filled a coverage gap in depth range between previously collected airborne bathymetric lidar to -50 m and multibeam coverage previously collected on R/V *Sonne* Cruise SO256.

Multibeam mapping seaward of Heron/One Tree revealed a drowned reef system with terraces and knickpoints consistent with stepped cycles of sea level regression and transgression that can be correlated regionally (Figure 4).

Sediment samples were collected from the bedforms using a small Eckman grab sampler with a camera and light attached to image the seafloor on sample collection (Figure 5). Sediments from the bedforms comprised of mixed siliciclastic (12 to 40% CaCO₃) gravelly sand (Table 2).

Figure 5: (L-R) Eckman grab sampler used on FK201122 (opening size ~30 cm x 30 cm); snapshot of the seabed during sample collection; a representative sample image.

Sample_ID	Survey_Area	%Gravel	%Sand	%Mud	%Caco3_Bulk
FK201122_1_GR18	1	2.2	97.3	0.4	12.5
FK201122_1_GR19	1	17.2	82.1	0.7	18.6
FK201122_1_GR20	1	20.4	79.4	0.2	39.4
FK201122_3_GR01	3	0.3	50.5	49.2	76.0
FK201122_3_GR02	3	0.1	49.1	50.9	78.7
FK201122_3_GR03	3	0.8	62.7	36.5	83.9
FK201122_3_GR04	3	0.4	53.3	46.3	78.0
FK201122_3_GR05	3	0.4	54.2	45.4	80.3
FK201122_3_GR06	3	2.0	62.8	35.2	82.3
FK201122_3_GR07	3	1.2	62.0	36.8	83.7
FK201122_3_GR08	3	1.6	60.2	38.2	81.4
FK201122_3_GR09	3	7.0	51.5	41.5	82.2
FK201122_3_GR10	3	2.6	58.2	39.2	78.8
FK201122_3_GR11	3	1.8	31.5	66.6	82.0
FK201122_3_GR12	3	1.2	56.3	42.5	82.1
FK201122_3_GR13	3	0.6	44.3	55.2	81.4
FK201122_3.1_GR14	5	3.3	13.5	83.2	43.2
FK201122_3.1_GR15	5	6.6	30.5	62.9	59.0
FK201122_3.1_GR16	5	11.3	31.2	57.6	61.9
FK201122_3.1_GR17	5	0.1	50.0	49.9	68.0

Table 2: Preliminary sediment grain size and %CaCO₃ results.

Survey Area 2

Systematic mapping in area 2 aimed to identify and map the full connection between an underfilled paleo-channel observed in previously collected airborne lidar bathymetry data, and characteristics of the termination of the paleo-Fitzroy River channel and delta (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Survey area 2; paleo-Fitzroy river channel and termination, and Capricorn Channel -90 m drowned shoreline.

Mapping to the south and north of the paleo-Fitzroy River has revealed the characteristics and extent of -90 m reef terraces and an extensive drowned shoreline with remnant sub-parallel linear ridges consistent with a coastal strandplain (Figure 7). The strandplain dunes have a height amplitude of 10-12 m and are assumed to be at least partially indurated (cemented) to remain preserved (Figure 8). Poor weather hampered the completion of systematic mapping of the paleo-Fitzroy channel. A typical river-mouth delta was not observed within the survey area, however, the new mapping data will contribute to a better understanding of sediment routing from the shelf to the slope.

Figure 7: (L-R), partially complete mapping of the paleo-Fitzroy river channel; survey area of the 'mouth' of the paleo-Fitzroy river; well-preserved linear sub-parallel drowned shoreline ridges indicative of a coastal strandplain.

Figure 8: Profile across a section of preserved drowned strandplain ridges with height amplitudes up to 12 m.

Survey Area 3

Ooid shoals are rare in the modern Great Barrier Reef, but may have been more extensive in the southern Great Barrier Reef during the LGM sea-level lowstand. Evidence of a drowned ooid shoal near the entrance of the Capricorn Channel was discovered in the late 1970s.

Systematic mapping and sediment sampling of the area (Figure 9) was undertaken to identify if there was a seabed surface expression of these deposits that might be analogous to the modern/Holocene ooid shoals of the Bahamas. Thirteen sediment samples were collected in depths ranging from -115 to -127 m, all of which contained abundant relict ooids (Figure 10). Grain size and %CaCO₃ results are shown in Table 2.

Figure 9: Systematic mapping at the entrance to the Capricorn Channel drowned ooid shoal, with locations of sediment grab samples.

Figure 10: Representative example of ooid-rich sediment samples collected at survey area 3 in -120 m depth. The brown spherical polished grains are relict ooids. White grains are modern carbonate bioclastic sediments, with minor lithics. The petri dish (left) is 10 cm diameter.

Survey Area 4

Systematic multibeam mapping seaward of the southern Swain Reefs has revealed a series of drowned reefs parallel to the present-day Swain Reefs margin (Figure 11). These reefs and deeper paleo-shoreline features are generally linear to cusped geometry, and oriented perpendicular to the prevailing south-east trade wind direction. Reef crests (drowned) are well-developed on the windward side (Figure 12). These reef geometries show stepped terraces and pinnacles at depths consistent with sea level-associated reef growth and can be correlated with the Capricorn-Bunker shelf-edge reefs and others regionally.

Figure 11: Systematic multibeam mapping of survey area 4, seaward of the present-day southern Swain Reefs margin. Existing multibeam was previously collected on RV Sonne cruise SO256.

Figure 12: Profile section across a drowned reef in survey area 4 showing terraces, pinnacles and knick points at depths consistent with the Capricorn-Bunker shelf-edge reefs and regionally.

Survey Area 5

Multibeam mapping along an enigmatic feature, colloquially known as the “Capricorn 200 m Cliff” was undertaken to better understand the extent and characteristics of this linear cliff-like feature at the -200m isobath (Figure 13). A profile section across the feature (Figure 14) shows that the cliff is approximately 80 m high. The top surface expression is rough in texture, which may be indicative of either a drowned relict reef, or a modern mesophotic reef. The seabed at the base of the cliff is comprised of soft sediment with spectacular current-induced bedforms potentially representing contourite features. The bedforms have amplitudes from 10 m to 50 m height (Figure 14) and are assumed to be active. Sediment samples were collected from the top and base of the cliff (Table 2, Figure 15).

Figure 13: Multibeam mapping in survey area 5, the 200 m 'Capricorn Cliff' with locations of sediment samples.

Figure 14: Section profiles across the cliff feature and along the base showing probable contourite bedforms.

Figure 15: Sediment grab sample images from the Capricorn Cliff (L-R); The rough top surface at approximately -180 m depth showing mesophotic biogenic growth; coral skeletal fragments collected in the top surface grab sample (scale 1cm increments); mixed carbonate-siliciclastic gravelly muddy sand from the base of the cliff.

Survey Area 6

During the return transit to the Port of Brisbane, the remaining survey time was maximized to fill multibeam coverage gaps linking the shelf-edge to the Fraser Canyon, upper continental slope and basin (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Survey area 6 systematically mapped the upper continental slope linking the shelf-edge to the previously mapped Fraser Canyon, and offshore basin.

A series of feeder gullies and channels were mapped, showing detailed sediment transport pathways from the continental shelf-edge near Lady Elliot Island, to the slope and Fraser Canyon system (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Feeder gullies linking the continental shelf-edge to the upper slope and Fraser Canyon.

2.2 Post Expedition Activities and Accomplishments

Sediment samples were analyzed for grain size distribution and percentage of carbonate at Queensland University of Technology. Sediment metadata and analytical results were submitted to the National Marine Sediments Database at Geoscience Australia.

Multibeam datasets were submitted to AusSeabed and have been uploaded to the public portal for discovery and accessibility. Initially released at 64 m grid resolution for the entire survey, the data have recently been reprocessed and republished at a range of grid resolutions from 2 m to 64 m.

Shapefiles and ship track information were submitted to the Queensland Research Infrastructure cloud and are publicly available.

Preliminary mapping and results were presented at the *Submerged Paleolandscapes of the Southern Hemispheres SHINE 2021 Workshop*. Additionally, talks and webinars (e.g., AusSeabed Showcase) have been presented by PI's McNeil, Beaman, and Brooke.

In 2022, PI's McNeil, Webster, Nothdurft, and Bostock made a second transit across the 200 m Capricorn Cliff on R/V *Investigator*, voyage IN2022_V07. The voyage collected a sub-bottom profile and new towed video camera imagery along the top of the cliff. Those data will be used to supplement ongoing projects to continue efforts to better understand the Capricorn and southern Great Barrier Reef region from a geological and paleo-environmental perspective.

The mapping and data collected supported two Australian Marine National Facility ship time proposals on board R/V *Investigator* to continue working in the southern Great Barrier Reef and Capricorn region. The most recent proposal includes indigenous sea country Traditional Owners in the design, development, and implementation of the proposed study. If successful, the voyage will reconstruct the evolution of the traditional sea country through the late Quaternary, mapping submerged features that represent significant sites of occupation and song lines.

Mapping and data have also supported Australian Research Council Discovery proposal submissions, led by PI's Nothdurft and Bostock to further progress the science questions and outcomes proposed in this voyage.

PI Brooke has led a chapter on Australian submerged dunes, with PI McNeil as a co-author, as part of a new global edited book series. The chapter includes data from the expedition and is currently in peer-review.

Students are using data to map the geomorphology of drowned reefs and shelf-edge terraces across the southern Great Barrier Reef and examine correlations with reef features in the northern Great Barrier Reef.

Additional data, being stored at Queensland University of Technology by PI Ristovski, will contribute to the Reef Restoration and Adaptation Program's atmospheric and cloud-seeding 'cooling and shading' projects.

3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of the date of this report's publication.

Data Type	Curator	Completed
Vessel underway data (CTD, Multibeam sonar, etc.)	Rolling Deck to Repository	Yes
Multibeam Bathymetry processed	AusSeaBed <i>The metadata description can be found here.</i>	Yes
ADCP	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Yes
Sediment samples	Geoscience Australia MARS Database <i>search keyword FK201122</i>	Yes
Atmospheric aerosol data	Queensland University of Technology Reef Restoration and Adaptation Program	No
Shapefiles and ship track	QRIS Cloud public	Yes

Table 3: List of all publicly available data.

4 Publications

No Pandemic-pause for Multi-disciplinary Reef Exploration in 2020. *Reef in Review* 2021. (50):8-10. <https://australiancoralreefsociety.org/library/reefinreview/>

Beaman RJ, Picard K, Miller AK. RV *Falkor* Surveys in Australia 2020-2021. Presented at: Australasian Hydrographic Society; February 17, 2022; Cairns, Australia. Accessed April 29, 2024. <https://www.deepreef.org/2022/02/17/rv-falkor-hydrospatial/>.

McNeil M, Nothdurft L, Webster JM, Brooke B, Beaman RJ. Preliminary exploration of the southern Great Barrier Reef Ice Age submerged palaeoshorelines and drowned coral reefs. Presented at: SHINE 2021 Workshop. https://schmidtocean.org/wp-content/uploads/McNeil_SHINE2021_abstract.pdf

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Mardi McNeil	Queensland University of Technology, University of Sydney School of Geosciences
Jody Webster*	University of Sydney
Robin Beaman*	James Cook University
Helen Bostock*	University of Queensland
Luke Nothdurft*	Queensland University of Technology
Luke Cravigan*	Queensland University of Technology
Zoran Ristovski*	Queensland University of Technology
Brendan Brooke*	Geoscience Australia
Ben Houseman	University of Queensland
Ella Sinclair	Queensland University of Technology
Haydn Trounce	Queensland University of Technology
Taloi Havini	Artist at Sea
Kim Picard#	Geoscience Australia

Table 4. List of scientists and students aboard R/V *Falkor*.

*non-sailing Principal Investigator

#non-sailing collaborator – AusSeabed multibeam processing & publication

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Beaman, R. (2021) [Schmidt Ocean Institute R/V *Falkor* Australia Campaign 2020-2021](#). Oral Presentation and Conference Paper, Sub-Committee on Regional Undersea Mapping, General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans, Virtual from Paris, France.

Beaman, R., Picard, K., and Miller, A. (2022). *RV Falkor* Surveys in Australia 2020-2021. Oral Presentation and Conference Paper, Hydrospatial 2021 Conference, Australasian Hydrographic Society, Cairns, Australia.

McNeil, M., Nothdurft, Lk, Webster, J., Brooke, B., and Beaman, R. (2021). [Preliminary Exploration of the Southern Great Barrier Reef Ice Age Submerged and Drowned Coral Reefs](#), Oral Presentation, Submerged Paleolandscapes of the Southern Hemispheres SHINE 2021 Workshop, virtual.

Taloi Havini solo exhibition: TBA21-Academy, Ocean Space Venice, May – October 2021; [The Soul Expanding Ocean #1: Taloi Havini Answer to the Call](#).

3.3 Cruise Records

- [Cruise Logs](#).

3.4 Media and Outreach

- [Cosmos Magazine: Mapping the undersea landscape of the reef \(2020\)](#).
- [Medium, The Labs: Ice Age Geology of the Great Barrier Reef: Field Research and Student Experience \(2020\)](#).
- [Wallpaper: Taloi Havini's first sonic work dunks the listener in an ocean of sound \(2021\)](#).
- [Financial Times: Deep listening – Taloi Havini conjures the sound of her ancestors at Venice Biennale \(2021\)](#).
- [Vanity Fair Italy: A Venezia l'installazione di Taloi Havini per sentire lo spirito dell'oceano \(2021\)](#).
- [Art Talkers: Ascoltare l'Oceano: Taloi Havini a Venezia \(2021\)](#).
- [Beaman, McNeil, and Brooke – several AusSeabed Showcase and Webinars](#).
- [Bostock – community consultation with southern Great Barrier Reef / Capricorn Darumbal and Woppaburra Traditional Owner groups](#).